

CATION-EXCHANGE MEASUREMENTS IN THE SOLID PHASE

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Soils are capable of delivering nutrients or metal ions at a much lower moisture status than what is obtained in the pasty condition. Since exchange, if any, in the air-dry state will be very small, it has been studied by using radioactive gold ions, introduced as an exchangeable cation into the clay. The exchange of gold ion has been studied against Na- and Ca-clays by maintaining (i) one of the phases in the solid state and (ii) both the phases in the solid state. In (ii) exchange does take place but to a very small extent, whereas in (i) the exchange is quite appreciable.

It has become apparent from the studies of various workers that both cations and anions take part in exchange of soils and clays, and that a considerable amount of these ions can be made available to the growing plants by exchange.

That direct contact of the exchange material and the exchanging ion is not essential for exchange has been demonstrated amongst others by Brown and Albrecht (*Res. Bull.*, No. 477, College of Agric. Mo., 1950) and Chatterjee (*Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1954, 2, 111). They have shown that the suspension of a cation-saturated clay and a moistened acid resin can exchange their cations even when the two are separated by a cellophane membrane. The isotherm obtained is similar to that usually found in exchange reactions. This may be interpreted by considering exchange of ions present essentially in the double layers of the two systems.

It has been shown by Bradfield (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 340) that Na-saturated clays can take up enough Ba^{2+} ions from an aqueous suspension of $BaSO_4$. As the equilibrium between solid $BaSO_4$ and the solution is disturbed, more and more adsorption may take place. Similarly from anorthite Ca^{2+} ions can be exchanged for H^+ ions of the clay (Graham, *Soil Sci.*, 1941, 51, 65). Kelley (*Proc. 1st. Int. Congr. Soil Sci.*, 1927, 4, 483) and later on Jenny, Overstreet and others (*Soil Sci.*, 1939, 47, 257) and Ayers (*ibid.*, 1939, 48, 9) have shown by means of tracer technique, that the exchange reaction is also possible in the solid phase, apparently without the presence of intermediate solution, termed by them as "contact exchange". This phenomenon is based on the assumption that the adsorbed ions are always oscillating, and whenever two exchange spots come closer to each other so that the oscillating zones overlap, both the ions may change their positions, resulting in an exchange.

In order to explore the possibility of exchange in the solid phase, the following experiments have been carried out. Since exchange is likely to be too small to be measured analytically, advantage has been taken of a radioactive tracer. The choice of the particular tracer has been restricted by the question of availability. We have used radioactive gold which has been obtained in a colloidal form.

EXPERIMENTAL

Radioactive gold was at first dissolved in aqua regia and the excess of acid and chlorine removed. It was then taken up several times with water and evaporated on

the water-bath. The radioactive gold chloride solution* was then added to the suspensions of Na- and Ca-clays, as a result of which partial exchange occurred. Free electrolytes were then removed by washing and the Au*-clay was dried and part of it made into solid blocks by mixing with polystyrene as a binder resin and hot-moulding in a hydraulic press. Similar blocks were made from Na- and Ca-clays.

The actual experiments consisted in allowing equilibration to proceed for 3-5 days** between the systems given below.

- (1) Na-clay block against Au*-clay block.
- (2) Ca-clay block against Au*-clay block.
- (3) Na-clay block against Au*-clay suspension.
- (4) Ca-clay block against Au*-clay suspension.
- (5) Au*-clay block in H-clay suspension.

In the experiments (1) and (2) one block was placed so tightly against the other by means of screw clips that the entire smooth surfaces came in contact with each other. In the experiments (3), (4) and (5), the solid clay blocks were suspended in the clay suspension. After the requisite number of days the blocks were washed thoroughly with water and oven-dried (105°) and the suspensions evaporated and similarly oven-dried. The blocks as well as the dried clays were then subjected to radioactive measurements which consisted of observing the β -counts. The results of these measurements are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

System.	Counting per minutes.
Background	20
1	62 (Na-clay blocks)
2	28 (Ca " "
3	1120 (Na " "
4	186 (Ca " "
5	220 (H-clay suspension)

DISCUSSION

It is clear from the above data that even if the two phases are present in the solid state (Expts. 1 and 2), noticeable amount of exchange takes place, i.e., Au³⁺ has ex-

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** Since the original radioactive gold solution has already decayed due to storage, the radioactivity of the Au*-clay is still weaker. Consequently, for the sake of expediency, the equilibrium has not been allowed beyond this period, even in the case of both the phases being solid, in which exchange is naturally much slower.

changed position with Na^+ and Ca^{2+} . These two experiments further show that Na^+ as expected, is exchanged to a greater extent than Ca^{2+} . Compared to the solid phase, Au^{*3+} is likely to knock off in suspension a much larger number of Na^+ or Ca^{2+} ions and hence, as experiments (3) and (4) show, the Na-clay and Ca-clay blocks give comparatively high counts. Here also the easy exchangeability of Na^+ in comparison to Ca^{2+} is clearly noticed. Similarly, by keeping the non-radioactive ion in the form of a suspension, as in experiment (5), the same effect is produced, viz., a greater exchange has taken place of H^+ for Au^{*3+} and hence a higher count of the final dried H-Au*-clay.

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